

ASSESSMENT OF QUASI-STATIC AND FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF UNI-DIRECTIONALLY FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMERS ON THE BASIS OF MATRIX EFFORT

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Abstract

Today the assessment of the load carrying capacity of uni-directionally (UD) fibre reinforced polymers (FRP) is carried out on ply level. Extensive material testing is required to determine the strength properties of each fibre-polymer-combination. In addition these strength properties depend on the state variables of the ply such as temperature, humidity and fibre volume content (FVC) as well as the interaction with neighbouring layers. The latter is a function of the stress ratio during fatigue testing, which increases the testing effort even further. Commonly this behaviour is taken into account by utilising complex piecewise linear Goodman diagrams.

In this paper a new approach is presented to describe the damage onset of the matrix as a first step for an enhanced strength and fatigue assessment and prediction. Stresses on lamina level are translated into stresses on the constituent level meaning fibre and matrix. Hence, the focus lies on the matrix behaviour mainly driving damage and fatigue behaviour of UD FRP. With the ability to express stresses and strains on matrix level a simplified description of strength as well as fatigue behaviour can be achieved. Because the matrix usually is an isotropic material an equivalent stress approach is legitimate and a simple symmetric Goodman diagram can be applied. This allows the definition of a matrix effort as the ratio between ambient and allowable stress. Furthermore, the state variables mentioned above are inherently taken into account. Hence the load carrying capacity becomes a function of temperature, moisture, FVC and other influences. Finally a general description of the succeeding phases of the damage and fatigue process of the lamina is given.

Keywords Fibre Reinforced Polymers; Strength; Fatigue; Matrix Damage Onset, Micro Mechanics, Composite.

1. Status Quo

Rotor blades for wind energy converters (WEC) kept growing in diameter over the last three decades. With the increase of length the structure is subject to scale effects. Hence, the surface of the blade, which is driving the aerodynamic forces on the blade, grows with the power of two with the rotor blade length. Meanwhile the mass of the blade is related to the volume of the blade structure which increases with the power of three when scaling up the blade length. This effect is called the square-cube-law first formulated by Galileo Galilei (1638). Due to improvements in the aerodynamic and composite design process the blade mass increases statistically with the power of 2.5 instead of 3 with the blade length.

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1.1. Design Driving Loads

The design driving forces in the rotor blade are in general aerodynamic forces and the inertia forces resulting from the structural mass of the rotor blade. For small blades up to rotor diameters of 80 m the quasi-static design loads which are mainly aerodynamic forces dominate the design. While for larger blades the fatigue design loads, hence the inertia forces, become dominant.

In Fig. 1 the damage equivalent loads (DEL) are compared to the serviceability limit state loads (SLSL) and the ultimate limit state loads (ULSL) for flap-wise bending moment M_y on the left hand side and for edge-wise bending moment M_x on the right hand side. To do so the design fatigue loads for the blades given in Markov matrices were transformed into DEL assuming an S/N curve exponent of $m = 10$ and a reference load cycle number of $n_{ref} = 1$. In the equation only the load amplitudes of the load combination i of design fatigue load L being a bending moments or lateral forces are taken into account.

$$L_{ref} = \left(\frac{\sum_i n_i L_{ia}^m}{n_{ref}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (1)$$

The designations for the rotor blades compared within Fig. 1 are given in Table 1. The order of the blades from left to right is from older to newer generation. For the flap-wise bending the fatigue loads in relation to the quasi-static loads (SLSL and ULSL) are increasing depending on the design lifetime and the spar cap (SC) material. The spar cap is the main reinforcement on the suction side (SS) and on the pressure side (PS) of the rotor blade. Only the EU167C25Y shows comparatively reduced fatigue loads since this blade is designed for offshore application, where aerodynamic loads predominate. Here the quasi-static design loads are significantly higher than the fatigue loads. It can be seen that the fatigue loads in flap-wise direction are up to twice as high as the SLSL. This ratio is even higher for the edge-wise loads where it reaches values of up to four.

Fig. 1 Comparison of DEL of EUROS blades (Krimmer, 2015)

This indicates that the fatigue loads in rotor blades for WEC are the main design driving forces in current and future constructions.

1.2. Definitions and Current Methods

Today, verification of FRP structures against fatigue loading is usually carried out utilising piecewise linear constant life diagrams (CLD) as shown in Fig. 2 (left). In contrast to isotropic metallic materials the allowable load cycle number for FRP is extremely dependent on the load ratio R_r , as defined by

$$R_r = \frac{\sigma_l}{\sigma_h}. \quad (2)$$

Herein σ_l is the lowest and σ_h is the highest stress during a load cycle. For isotropic materials symmetric CLD can be used. These are called Goodman diagrams and appear as shown within Fig. 2 (right). Since the fatigue behaviour is supposed to be symmetric regarding tensile and compressive loading, only the positive mean effort axis needs to be displayed.

Fig. 2 CLD from (Wedel-Heinen et al., 2006) (left), symmetric CLD (Goodman Diagram)

Table 1. Information from rotor blade designation of EUROS blades (Krimmer, 2015).

Designation	Rotor Diameter	SC Material	Design Lifetime
EU100G20Y	100 m	GFRP	20 Years
EU84G20Y	84 m	GFRP	20 Years
EU116G20Y	116 m	GFRP	20 Years
EU120G20Y	120 m	GFRP	20 Years
EU140C30Y	140 m	CFRP	30 Years
EU140G30Y	144 m	GFRP	30 Years
EU144C30Y	144 m	CFRP	30 Years
EU144G30Y	144 m	GFRP	30 Years
EU144C20Y	144 m	CFRP	20 Years
EU167C25Y	167 m	CFRP	25 Years

Within this paper the loading of a material is not given in terms of stresses but in terms of efforts e meaning an ambient stress σ in relation to an allowable stress R (fracture resistance), here being the tensile strength $R^{(+)}$. As a result the effort is generally defined as

$$e = \frac{\sigma}{R^{(+)}}. \quad (3)$$

Further the mean effort e_m of a load cycle represents the relation between the mean stress σ_m of a load cycle and the tensile strength of the material. The same is done for the amplitude effort e_a as well as the highest and the lowest effort e_h and e_l during a load cycle.

$$e_m = \frac{\sigma_m}{R^{(+)}}, e_a = \frac{\sigma_a}{R^{(+)}}, e_h = \frac{\sigma_h}{R^{(+)}} \text{ and } e_l = \frac{\sigma_l}{R^{(+)}} \quad (4)$$

Hereby the loading of a material can be expressed as a value between zero and one, where one means that a damage is initiated within the material.

Although early during fatigue testing of GFRP coupons crack initiation can be observed (Brøndsted, 2016), usually only the number of load cycles until failure of a specimen is recorded together with the mean and the amplitude stress. Hence the process of damage initiation, degradation and failure needs to be investigated more thoroughly.

Throughout this paper FRP are understood as glass or carbon fibres embedded in a polymer matrix e.g. epoxy resin. The FRP is built up from multiple uni-directional (UD) layers called laminae. These laminae can have different directions. A lamina is build up from a material out of the constituents fibre and matrix.

2. Fatigue Assessment of Fibre Reinforced Plastics

As indicated in the introduction, the process of damage, degradation and failure, all together called fatigue of FRP, needs to be investigated in more detail. Thus for this paper the following subdivision of the process is defined:

- (1) Stage 1: Loading of the undamaged lamina. No increase of crack density due to loading is observed up to the point of initiation of damage. This point is called damage onset and defines the start point for stage 2
- (2) Stage 2: Loading during degradation stage. An increase of crack density due to loading can be observed. This is valid for all load cycles after damage onset up to the point of failure, which is defined as stage 3.
- (3) Stage 3: Failure is understood as the loss of load carrying capacity, which is defined by the load that introduces a strain energy higher than the residual allowable strain energy of the laminae.

Beyond the point of damage onset, the assumption of linear elasticity is not valid, since cracks are initiated. Depending on the direction of the lamina strain, the cracks will open or close during loading. When opening, the load carrying cross section is reduced, leading to a decrease in the stiffness of the material. When closing, the contacting crack surfaces provide a load transferring capability. Only a slight reduction in stiffness will result. At the same time energy will dissipate due to friction between the crack surfaces, leading to an increase in temperature. This will reduce the material properties of the matrix in terms of Young's modulus and strength. As a consequence the degradation will be accelerated.

To reliably predict the load carrying capability of a composite during fatigue loading, it is clear that the point of damage onset needs to be known. A method to predict that point is presented in the following chapters.

2.1. Coordinate Systems

Since a lamina is made of transversely isotropic material, the material properties are defined in the longitudinal direction L parallel to the fibres and in the direction T transverse to the fibres.

The lamina is defined in a Cartesian coordinate system (COS) x_1, x_2, x_3 where the 1-axis coincides with the L -axis of the material, the x_2 -axis of the lamina is defined within the lamina plane while the x_3 -axis is perpendicular to axis x_1 and x_2 and defines the lamina thickness direction.

For the laminate the properties are given within a Cartesian x, y, z COS where axes x and y are perpendicular to each other, both lying within the laminate plane. The z -axis is perpendicular to the x and the y -axis and is oriented in the laminate thickness direction. Axis x_3 and z coincide while for each layer i the angle of rotation about the z -axis between x -axis and x_1 -axis is α_i . For the present work the x_1, x_2, x_3 COS as shown in Fig. 3 is of main interest.

Fig. 3 Coordinate system of the lamina (Krimmer, 2014)

2.2. Elastic Properties of the Lamina

Based on the following assumptions the elastic properties of a lamina can be calculated according to (Krimmer, 2014):

- All fibres are cylindrical and have the same and constant radius
- Adjacent fibres are parallel
- The fibres are in regular hexagonal array
- Fibres and matrix are ideally connected to each other
- Effects of interface and interphase are negligible
- The material is transversally isotropic as a result of the preceding assumptions.

The Young's modulus in transverse direction is given by

$$E_T = \frac{2E_M}{\sqrt{3}} \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}} - \frac{\pi}{2\left(1-\frac{E_M}{E_{FT}}\right)} + \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} + \arctan\left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}\left(1-\frac{E_M}{E_{FT}}\right)}}{\sqrt{1-2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}\left(1-\frac{E_M}{E_{FT}}\right)^2}}\right)}{\left(1-\frac{E_M}{E_{FT}}\right)\sqrt{1-2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}\left(1-\frac{E_M}{E_{FT}}\right)^2}} \right]. \quad (5)$$

Here E_M is the Young's modulus of the matrix, E_{FT} is the Young's modulus of the fibre in transverse direction and φ is the fibre volume content (FVC). Based on that, the in-situ Young's modulus of the matrix in transverse direction can be calculated by

$$E'_{MT} = \frac{E_{FL}\left(\frac{E_T}{E_M}(1-v'_{MT})^2 + v'_{MT}\right)\varphi + E_T(1-\varphi)}{\frac{E_{FL}}{E_M}\left(\frac{E_T}{E_M}(1-3v'_{MT})^2 - 2v'_{MT}\right) + 2(v'_{MT})^2 + v'_{MT}} \text{ with } v'_{MT} = \left(1 - \frac{(v_{FLT} + v_{FTT})E_M}{v_M(E_{FL} + E_{FT})}\right) v_M. \quad (6)$$

The apostrophe indicates that the transverse strain blocking of the matrix (TSB) due to the embedded fibres is taken into account. The in-situ Young's modulus of the matrix in longitudinal direction results from

$$E'_{ML} = \frac{E_T(1-v'_{ML}) + E_M v'_{ML}}{\frac{E_T}{E_M}(1-v'_{ML}) + v'_{ML} + 2v'_{ML}\left(1-\frac{E_T}{E_M}\right)} \text{ with } v'_{ML} = \left(1 - \frac{(v_{FTL} E_M)}{v_M E_{FT}}\right) v_M. \quad (7)$$

Now the Young's modulus of the lamina in longitudinal direction under consideration of TSB of the matrix is given by

$$E'_1 = E'_L = E_{FL}\varphi + E'_{ML}(1 - \varphi). \quad (8)$$

Also, under consideration of the TSB of the matrix, the transverse Young's modulus of the lamina results from

$$E_2 = E_3 = E'_T = \frac{2E'_M}{\sqrt{3}} \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}} - \frac{\pi}{2\left(1 - \frac{E'_M}{E_{FT}}\right)} + \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} + \arctan\left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{E'_M}{E_{FT}}\right)}{\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{E'_M}{E_{FT}}\right)}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{E'_M}{E_{FT}}\right)\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{E'_M}{E_{FT}}\right)} \right]. \quad (9)$$

The in-situ shear moduli of the matrix can be calculated by

$$G'_{MLT} = \frac{E'_{MT} + E'_{ML}}{4(1 + \nu_M)} \text{ and } G'_{MTT} = \frac{E'_{MT}}{2(1 + \nu_{MTT})} \text{ with } \nu_{MTT} = \nu_M \frac{1 + \varphi\left(\frac{E_{FL}}{E_M}(1 + \nu_{MT}) - 1\right)}{1 + \varphi\left(\frac{E_{FL}}{E_M}(1 + \nu_{MT}^2\left(\frac{E_M}{E_T} - 1\right)) - 1\right)} \quad (10)$$

Now the shear moduli for the longitudinal-transverse direction G'_{LT} can be calculated with

$$G_{12} = G_{13} = G'_{LT} = \frac{2G'_{MLT}}{\sqrt{3}} \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}} - \frac{\pi}{2\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MLT}}{G_{FLT}}\right)} + \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} + \arctan\left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MLT}}{G_{FLT}}\right)}{\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MLT}}{G_{FLT}}\right)}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MLT}}{G_{FLT}}\right)\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MLT}}{G_{FLT}}\right)} \right] \quad (11)$$

And G'_{TT} for the transverse-transverse direction.

$$G_{23} = G'_{TT} = \frac{2G'_{MTT}}{\sqrt{3}} \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}} - \frac{\pi}{2\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MTT}}{G_{FTT}}\right)} + \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} + \arctan\left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MTT}}{G_{FTT}}\right)}{\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MTT}}{G_{FTT}}\right)}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MTT}}{G_{FTT}}\right)\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MTT}}{G_{FTT}}\right)} \right] \quad (12)$$

Finally the Poisson's ratio ν_{TL} of the lamina results from the linear rule of mixture (ROM), ν_{LT} from the application of Maxwell's Theorem, and ν_{TT} from the assumption of transverse isotropy.

$$\nu_{TL} = \varphi\nu_{FTL} + (1 - \varphi)\nu_M, \nu_{LT} = \nu_{TL}\frac{E'_T}{E'_L} \text{ and } \nu_{TT} = \frac{E'_T}{2G'_{TT}} - 1 \quad (13)$$

These ROM are compared to the upper bound of the Hashin and Rosen (1964) formulation for CFRP in Fig. 4 and for GFRP in Fig. 5. The fibre and resin properties utilized for calculation of the material properties within this work are given in Table 2. Obviously the ROM of the present work show good correlation with the upper bound of the Hashin and Rosen formulation. Only the transverse-transverse Poisson's ratio shows a certain deviation. The main advantage of the ROM introduced here is the explicit determination of the in-situ properties

Fig. 4 Comparison of Hashin and Rosen formulation with present model for CFRP

Fig. 5 Comparison of Hashin and Rosen formulation with present model for GFRP

of the matrix. These are required later on to calculate the transferring function from lamina to constituent stresses.

Table 2. Constituent properties used for material model calculation

Material	E_L in GPa	E_T in GPa	G_{LT} in GPa	G_{TT} in GPa	ν_{TL} in 1	ν_{TT} in 1	$R_L^{(+)}$ in MPa
CF HT	230	14.7	47.6	4.96	0.33	0.49	3600
GF E-CR	81.5	81.5	33.5	33.5	0.22	0.22	2290
Epoxy Resin	3.09	3.09	1.13	1.13	0.37	0.37	73.5

2.3. Matrix Stresses in the Lamina

Today, the load carrying capacity of lamina is assessed using strength criteria (Puck, 1996), (Tsai and Wu, 1971) based on the strength properties of the lamina. The basis for this approach is the assumption of a quasi-homogeneous orthotropic material behaviour. Hence, the basic strength properties of a lamina are determined through material testing. Usually those are the tensile and the compressive strength in longitudinal direction $R_L^{(+)}$ and $R_L^{(-)}$, the tensile and the compressive strength in transverse direction $R_T^{(+)}$ and $R_T^{(-)}$ and the shear strength in longitudinal-transverse and in transverse-transverse direction of the lamina R_{LT} and R_{TT} .

Though many of the test results show significant non-linear stress-strain behaviour, and micro-cracking already occurs at small strains, only the catastrophic failure is considered. Surprisingly, considerable non-linear behaviour can be observed when testing for matrix dominated properties in directions that show comparatively high stresses at failure. Those are

- Shear testing in longitudinal-transverse direction
- Shear testing in transverse-transverse direction
- Compressive testing in transverse direction

To further understand this behaviour, it is proposed to distinguish between the loading of the matrix and the loading of the fibres instead of making the assumption of a quasi-homogeneous orthotropic material. This can be done by formulating the constituent stresses as functions of the lamina stresses. To not underestimate the constituent stresses, the in-situ properties of the matrix as derived above are required.

In fibre direction the fibre and the matrix can be understood as a parallel array of the two materials. The array is shown schematically in Fig. 6 (left). By this assumption, the matrix stress in x_1 direction can be expressed as

Fig. 6 Parallel array for longitudinal direction (left) and serial array for transverse direction (right) of fibre and matrix

$$\sigma_{M1} = \frac{\sigma_1}{E_L} E'_{ML}. \quad (14)$$

The matrix stress in x_2 and x_3 direction as per the model shown in Fig. 6 (right) can be calculated by

$$\sigma_{M2} = \frac{\sigma_2}{E'_T \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}}}{E_{FT}} + \frac{(1-\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}})}{E'_{MT}} \right)} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{M3} = \frac{\sigma_3}{E'_T \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}}}{E_{FT}} + \frac{(\sqrt{3}-\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}})}{E'_{MT}} \right)}. \quad (15)$$

The shear stresses in the matrix in x_{21} and in x_{31} direction are calculated by

$$\tau_{M21} = \frac{\tau_{21}}{G'_{LT} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}}}{G_{FLT}} + \frac{(1-\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}})}{G_{MLT}} \right)} \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_{M31} = \frac{\tau_{31}}{G'_{LT} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}}}{G_{FLT}} + \frac{(\sqrt{3}-\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}})}{G_{MLT}} \right)}. \quad (16)$$

And the shear stress in x_{23} direction is calculated by

$$\tau_{M23} = \frac{\tau_{23}}{G'_{TT} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}}}{G_{FTT}} + \frac{(1-\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}})}{G_{MTT}} \right)}. \quad (17)$$

For the fibre stresses the same formulae apply substituting the index M for matrix in the stress values σ and τ by the index F for fibre. In this work the matrix stresses are given since the matrix behaviour is dominant regarding fatigue of the lamina.

2.4. Damage Criterion and Damage Function for the Lamina

Now the matrix stress vector as function of the lamina stress vector can be formulated. The stresses in a lamina can be divided into residual stresses σ_R , resulting from stresses between the laminae due to hygrothermal and polymer-physical strain effects, and stresses from external loads σ_E . Finally, thermal strains, moisture induced strains and strains due to polymer-physical shrinkage within the matrix are introduced. With the resulting formula the 3D stress state can be calculated in a matrix element within the lamina, taking into account residual stresses due to thermal effects, moisture and the shrinkage of the matrix by polymer-physical effects during the curing process.

$$\{\sigma_M\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{M1} \\ \sigma_{M2} \\ \sigma_{M3} \\ \tau_{M23} \\ \tau_{M31} \\ \tau_{M21} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\sigma_{1E} + \sigma_{1R}}{E_L} E'_{ML} \\ \frac{\sigma_{2E} + \sigma_{2R}}{E'_T \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}}}{E_{FT}} + \frac{(1-\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}})}{E'_{MT}} \right)} \\ \frac{\sigma_{3E} + \sigma_{3R}}{E'_T \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}}}{E_{FT}} + \frac{(\sqrt{3}-\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}})}{E'_{MT}} \right)} \\ \frac{\tau_{23E} + \tau_{23R}}{G'_{TT} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}}}{G_{FTT}} + \frac{(1-\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}})}{G_{MTT}} \right)} \\ \frac{\tau_{31E} + \tau_{31R}}{G'_{LT} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}}}{G_{FLT}} + \frac{(\sqrt{3}-\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}})}{G_{MLT}} \right)} \\ \frac{\tau_{21E} + \tau_{21R}}{G'_{LT} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}}}{G_{FLT}} + \frac{(1-\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\rho}{\pi}})}{G_{MLT}} \right)} \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} (\alpha_{MT}\Delta T + \alpha_{MM}\Delta M + \alpha_{MP})E_M \quad (18)$$

Therefore the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) α_{MT} , the coefficient of expansion due to moisture (CME) α_{MM} and the coefficient of polymer-physical expansion (CPE) α_{MP} have to be identified. Additional input

parameters are the temperature difference ΔT between temperature at curing and operating temperature and the relative moisture in terms of

$$\Delta M = \frac{m_{\text{wet}} - m_{\text{dry}}}{m_{\text{dry}}}. \quad (19)$$

Since isotropic behaviour can be assumed for the matrix, a classical strain energy approach can be taken and the equivalent stress in the 3D matrix element within a lamina can be calculated as first formulated by Beltrami (1885).

$$\sigma_{\text{Me}} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{M1}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{M2}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{M3}}^2 - 2\nu_{\text{M}}(\sigma_{\text{M1}}\sigma_{\text{M2}} + \sigma_{\text{M2}}\sigma_{\text{M3}} + \sigma_{\text{M3}}\sigma_{\text{M1}}) + 2(1 + \nu_{\text{M}})(\tau_{\text{M21}}^2 + \tau_{\text{M31}}^2 + \tau_{\text{M23}}^2)} \quad (20)$$

The effort e_{M} of the matrix under a given stress vector can now be calculated in terms of the equivalent stress and the tensile strength of the matrix.

$$e_{\text{M}} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{Me}}}{R_{\text{M}}^{(+)}} \quad (21)$$

An effort of the matrix within the lamina of $0 \leq e_{\text{M}} < 1$ results from an allowable state of stress, that leaves the matrix undamaged. An effort of $e_{\text{M}} \geq 1$ leads to formation of cracks in the matrix. As a consequence the damage criterion for the lamina is given by

$$\frac{\sigma_{\text{Me}}}{R_{\text{M}}^{(+)}} = 1. \quad (22)$$

Cracking of the matrix does not necessarily lead to failure of the lamina, which may still have a finite load carrying capacity. That means that the given formulae are not assessing failure but damage onset within a lamina due to matrix cracking.

As stated previously, a similar approach can be taken for the fibre. Therefore, the index M in the formulae for the stresses σ and τ , the effort e and the fracture resistance R needs to be substituted by the index F for fibre.

2.5. Fatigue Assessment for the Lamina

Based on the presented approach to determine constituent stresses from lamina stresses, an assessment of the fatigue effort of laminae is possible. Usually the fatigue loading of a structure is given as moments and forces in terms of Markov matrices containing a load cycle number n_i for the combination of an amplitude loading L_{ia} with a mean loading L_{im} , where L_i can denote both moments and forces. Then the global loading of the structure can be transferred into the stresses of a laminate element, further into the local stresses in the lamina, and finally into constituent stresses.

The following paragraph explains the method to determine the fatigue effort of the matrix. But it can also be applied to the fibre. Now, the fatigue loading of the matrix is given as an amplitude stress vector $\{\sigma_{\text{Mia}}\}$ and a mean stress vector $\{\sigma_{\text{Mim}}\}$ together with the load cycle number n_i of this stress combination. These are further transferred into the efforts e_{Mia} and e_{Mim} . Based on the linear Goodman diagram as shown in Fig. 2 (right) and knowing the S/N-curve exponent m of the resin matrix allows the calculation of an allowable load cycle number N_{Mi} for the stress combination i within the matrix.

$$N_{\text{Mi}} = \left(\frac{1 - e_{\text{Mim}}}{e_{\text{Mia}}} \right)^m \quad (23)$$

The damage effective increment due to the load combination i is given by

$$D_{\text{Mi}} = \frac{n_i}{N_{\text{Mi}}}. \quad (24)$$

Assuming that damage accumulation according to Palmgren (1924) and Miner (1945) can be used, the damage in the matrix element can be calculated by

$$D_{\text{M}} = \sum_i D_{\text{Mi}}. \quad (25)$$

Now the fatigue effort of the matrix e_{Mf} is formulated.

$$e_{\text{Mf}} = D_{\text{M}}^{\left(\frac{1}{m}\right)} \quad (26)$$

Usually the polymer-physical shrinkage effect due to curing is included in the mean stress vector of the matrix. As long as the strain rate during external loading is much higher than the strain rate due to temperature change or moisture uptake, the hygrothermal stresses will be incorporated in the mean stress vector as well. In this case, the amplitude stress vector is comprised of stresses due to external loading only.

3. Summary and Outlook

An approach for the assessment of the effort of the matrix within lamina of FRP has been introduced. Thereby external and residual stresses acting on the lamina as well as hygrothermal and polymer-physical effects can be taken into account. Transferring functions from lamina stresses into constituent stresses are given. Based on these, a classical strain energy approach for the constituents fibre and matrix can be applied. Further, formulae are given to apply the approach to fatigue loading combinations on lamina within FRP leading to an expression of fatigue effort of the constituents.

The resulting effort expression can be interpreted as a fatigue saturation of the matrix that leads to matrix cracking when reaching a value of $e_{Mf} = 1$. This delivers information on the point of damage onset in the matrix within the composite under quasi-static and fatigue loading.

It is important to know that it only applies to lamina without undulation and without angle deviation. To take into account effects like these, the introduction of an adequate physically based parameter is necessary. The effect is more important in CFRP than in GFRP since the allowable strain in the carbon fibres is the limiting factor for CFRP regarding global strains in fibre direction. For GFRP the effect of undulation and angle deviation is not as important.

Depending on the load-carrying function of the structural member, it has to be decided whether matrix efforts above one are allowable. If so, this would imply that cracking or micro-cracking in the matrix would not compromise the load-carrying capacity of the structural member.

For the primary structure, mainly build up from UD FRP, cracking in the matrix appears to be critical and should thus be avoided. Within secondary structure, build up with two or more fibre directions, matrix cracking can be allowable. This decision requires further investigation of the damage, fatigue and failure process and careful engineering judgement.

As next steps the effects of fibre undulation on lamina properties as well as the effects of degradation of matrix properties on lamina behaviour will further be investigated to gain a deeper understanding of the process of damage, degradation and failure of FRP composites.

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